

Patient - Thomas "Tom" Movell (he/him)

"I've suffered some setbacks but it's still important for me to have control over my healthcare and to feel connected to others."

Bio

After serving several tours of duty in the army, Tom finished university and graduate school while working for a defense and aerospace contractor. He enjoys using technology to evaluate information, and being seen as a leader on the job, in his community and church, and at home. He recently turned 86 and has been living his retirement in great health, engaging in many physical activities including mowing the lawn and driving. Six months ago, he had a stroke and subsequent fall, which limited his ability to get around and to communicate as effectively as he likes. His impaired vision prevents him from using the Internet, email, or his phone for texting as he used to. He needs help getting to the bathroom, has a harder time with fine motor skills, and gets tired easily. He is still wholly in possession of his intellectual abilities.

Tom's daughter lives with him in his small Southern town, and he feels anxiety about the level of help she now provides him. He does not want to believe this is the "new normal" and has faith he'll regain his strength and way of life.

Education: BS, Engineering; MBA

Years of experience: 50+

Work location: Retired. Veteran. Former aerospace engineer, consultant

Health Conditions

- Excellent health until recently
- Suffered a stroke last year, which has impaired his communication, mobility, and vision, and limits his time online and reading
- A fall after his stroke stopped him from driving and visiting friends
- Some hearing loss; uses hearing aids daily

Healthcare influences

- Tom has regularly visited his nearby VA for years for physicals. He is an affable, articulate man who respects his doctors and takes their advice seriously
- Tom has always been physically active and does not engage in risky behaviors, but likes an occasional glass of wine

Goals

- Wants the ability to ask his pharmacist medication-related questions, but rarely leaves home since his stroke
- To keep the good relationship and dialogue he has with healthcare providers despite his new limitations
- To video chat with his doctors. He thrives on face-to-face interaction

Software attitude & use

- Tom has always been a technology adopter. He uses a laptop at home to communicate with friends and family, and to manage his healthcare
- Tom still wants to use email and access the Internet, but knows he can't as he did before his illness
- He'd like healthcare providers to provide the option for larger text online. He's a strong reader but would like more audio information from providers

Opportunities to connect

- Create online tools that make it easier to allow his daughter access to his health information
- Create options on mobile apps and online applications that allow for visual impairment and provide voice recognition
- Create applications that focus on social inclusion of the elderly or homebound

Wants/Needs

- **Control.** Tom wants a telehealth video chat service so he and his daughter can consult with providers together. His daughter can do this on her own, but he wants to keep autonomy and control as much as possible
- **Convenience.** A way to smartly schedule multiple appointments in one day, decreasing the need for Tom's daughter to miss much work
- **Connection.** Tom needs community connectedness even with impaired mobility
- **Support.** Aid accessing information and managing the demands of evolving health conditions

Support Network

Tom lives with his wife of over fifty years and with his eldest daughter. His wife has dementia and is not able to participate directly in his care. His daughter owns a business and while she feels like it is her "duty" to care for her father, she has had to hire visiting nurses to help with his care

VA doctors, local physicians and pharmacists, church groups, veterans' groups. Before his health turned, he was highly engaged in his community

Tom returned home after his stroke instead of going to a rehab facility and is visited by nurses and therapists regularly